

MILAN'S SOUTHERN MARGINS PROXIMITY PROJECT: TOWARDS EQUITABLE PUBLIC GREEN SPACES AS AN EVERYDAY LIFE INFRASTRUCTURE

Milano'nun Güney Çeperi İçin Yakınsama Projesi: Günlük Yaşamın Altyapısı Olarak Eşitlikçi Kamusal Yeşil Alanlara Doğru

Çağlanur KÖSEL¹

Deniz ÇAM¹

¹ Politecnico di Milano

Abstract

Proximity is a key urban concept related to accessibility and public services. Urban population concentration increases density, especially in city centres. Accordingly, while urban public services, which are the 'infrastructure of daily life', are concentrated in the central areas of cities, spatial inequalities in accessing essential facilities and services emerge in peri-urban areas. What are the urban design approaches that will provide equal access to public spaces, which are an important part of the daily lives of those living in peri-urban areas, not only physically but also in terms of quality and usability in line with the principle of "proximity"? This study focuses on analysing green spaces, which are an important component of urban public services, within the framework of this holistic "proximity" understanding. Milan, Italy's Lombardy capital and second most populous city, is the case study. Its Milan-Sud peri-urban region, marked by socio-environmental fragility, is the analysis focus. The study's methodology is based on macro and micro-scale spatial analyses of the study area, combined with findings from user interviews conducted during fieldwork. The findings showed that although some parks are accessible in terms of proximity to public services and users, they are not attractive, safe or functional enough. The research analysed the causes of these problems in detail in line with urban design principles and revealed the effects of the design of public green spaces. As a result, it aims to develop design recommendations for the solution of the 'proximity' problem experienced in public spaces where users living in urban peripheries can spend most of their daily lives. These proposals aim to increase not only accessibility but also the attractiveness, safety, functionality and social interaction between users.

Keywords: proximity, urban design, green spaces, peri-urban landscapes, Milano

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Correspondence | İletişim:
caglanur.kosel@mail.polimi.it

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Özet

Yakınlık, erişilebilirliği ve kamusal hizmetleri sorgulayan çağdaş kentsel alanda önemli bir kavramdır. Dünya nüfusunun büyük bölümünün kentsel alanlarda yoğunlaşması, özellikle kent merkezlerinde artan nüfus yoğunluğu ile mekânsal yoğunlaşmayı beraberinde getirmektedir. Dolayısıyla ‘günlük yaşamın altyapısı’ olan kentsel kamusal hizmetler de kentlerin merkez bölgesinde yoğunlaşırken, kentin çeper alanlarında temel olanaklara ve hizmetlere erişimde mekânsal eşitsizlikler ortaya çıkarabilmektedir. Kent çeperi alanlarda yaşayanların günlük yaşamlarının önemli bir parçası olan kamusal alanlara ‘yakınlık’ ilkesi doğrultusunda sadece fiziksel olarak değil, aynı zamanda nitelik ve kullanılabilirlik açısından da eşit erişimini sağlayacak kentsel tasarım yaklaşımları neler olabilir? Bu çalışma, kentsel kamusal hizmetlerin önemli bir bileşeni olan yeşil alanların bu bütüncül ‘yakınlık’ anlayışı çerçevesinde incelenmesine odaklanmaktadır. Vaka çalışması olarak, İtalya’nın *Lombardiya* bölgesinin başkenti ve ikinci en kalabalık şehri Milano tercih edilmiştir. Milano, çok yönlü fonksiyonları, morfolojik yapısı ve sosyal dinamikleriyle kentsel yaşamın yoğun olarak yaşandığı bir merkez iken, güney çeperinde yer alan ve sosyo-çevresel açıdan kırılgan nitelikteki *Milano-Sud* bölgesi, çalışmanın analiz odak noktasıdır. Çalışmanın yöntemi, çalışma alanının makro ve mikro ölçekli mekânsal analizleri ile saha çalışması ve kullanıcılarla yapılan görüşmelerin sonuçlarına dayanmaktadır. Bulgular, bazı parkların kamusal hizmetlere ve kullanıcılara yakınlık açısından erişilebilir olmasına rağmen, yeterince çekici, güvenli veya işlevsel olmadığını göstermiştir. Araştırma, kentsel tasarım ilkeleri doğrultusunda bu problemlerin nedenini detaylıca incelenmiş ve kamusal yeşil alanların tasarımının etkilerini ortaya koymuştur. Sonuç olarak bu çalışma, kent çeperlerinde yaşayanların günlük yaşamında önemli yer tutan kamusal alanların ‘yakınlık’ ilkesiyle erişilebilirliğini ve kullanılabilirliğini artıracak tasarım önerileri geliştirmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Bu öneriler, sadece erişilebilirliği değil, aynı zamanda bu alanların çekiciliğini, güvenliğini, işlevselliğini ve kullanıcılar arasındaki sosyal etkileşimi de artırmayı hedeflemektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: yakınlık, kentsel tasarım, yeşil alanlar, kent çeperi, Milano

1. INTRODUCTION

Proximity (or geographical closeness, propinquity) is an effective concept and a widespread word that has become fashionable in today's urban planning. 'Proximity', one of the fundamental elements of urban life, is the geographic closeness of people, services, and activities to each other (Gil Solá and Vilhelmson, 2018). However, while the importance of proximity in providing basic access is well documented, this study argues that mere physical proximity to public green spaces does not necessarily imply their active use and integration into the daily lives of urban residents. In particular, despite the presence of physically accessible green spaces in many urban areas, a significant proportion of these spaces are underutilised or fail to attract their intended beneficiaries. This discrepancy highlights a critical gap in our understanding of how proximity interacts with other factors, particularly those related to urban design and the social dynamics of space, to influence the actual use of public amenities. Therefore, in this study, ‘proximity’ is considered not only as a geographical phenomenon, but also in

the context of the potential relationship and interaction of users with public services. This proximity directly affects individuals' access to opportunities in the urban environment, as well as shapes their daily lives – which also expresses the relationship and interaction they establish with urban public services as the infrastructure of this daily life – and their well-being. At this point, the effect/formation referred to as shaping directly emphasizes the importance of urban design and urban planning and the necessity of the principle of being fair and equal in these areas. While making this emphasis, it is also necessary not to overlook that the concept of proximity establishes an extremely strong connection with accessibility. Proximity is one of the cornerstones of accessibility, which is defined as individuals' potential to reach activities that are important for their daily lives and well-being. However, this study questions the reasons why users prefer or do not prefer public spaces despite the presence of physical accessibility and aims to relate this situation to urban design factors. Therefore, it embraces that proximity is not just a physical phenomenon. This makes it possible to take proximity out of a narrow physical perspective and emphasise that it is one of the important points of the infrastructure of daily life in a multidimensional way, so the concept of proximity is a concept that has the potential to have a performative impact in many different dimensions that can be at the centre of discourses on reducing energy-consuming and polluting travel, developing local social ties, trust and capital, and stimulating economic activity and innovation (Boschma, 2005; Davoudi et al., 2008; Gil Solá and Vilhelmson, 2018; Handy, 2020).

Furthermore, the principles of sustainability and the implementation of green infrastructure are intrinsically linked to the concepts of proximity and equal access, which form the basis of this study. Sustainable urban design practices can enhance the attractiveness and usability of green spaces and thus encourage greater use even when physical proximity is present. For example, the integration of ecological features, the use of sustainable materials and designs that support biodiversity can create more engaging and healthy environments and positively influence user motivation and experience. Moreover, green infrastructure initiatives such as the creation of interconnected green corridors and improving ecological connectivity can increase the accessibility of green spaces for a wider range of users, including more marginalised or peri-urban areas. By considering sustainability not only as an environmental concern but as a framework for creating more liveable and attractive public spaces, this study aims to explore how sustainable design principles can address the problem of under-utilisation despite physical proximity and ultimately contribute to a more equitable and vibrant urban environment.

The role of proximity in urban planning is important for revitalising cities and creating compact urban areas. When it is emphasised that accessibility is not only physical proximity, pedestrian mobility and walkability come to the fore at this point. Practices where the proximity principle is adopted have enabled citizens to shift from using private cars in their daily lives to an approach that is more sensitive to their transport needs, shortens travel distances, supports local life, and encourages walking, cycling and public transport. In this context, today's planning research, which is in search of sustainability, frequently mentions that pedestrian mobility will play an even more important role in the cities of the future, and moreover, the importance of its role in creating liveable and sustainable cities (Cervero et al., 2009; Ewing and Clemente, 2013; Carmona, 2021; Belge and Ercan 2022).

Proximity should be considered as a complex concept that requires careful consideration of the relationship between actions at the local and urban scales (Marchigiani and Bonfantini, 2022). In a socio-spatial context, regaining a sense of belonging to places can reactivate community ties. This context is particularly critical in the case study. The case of Milano Sud has clearly demonstrated that physical proximity to a public service is not enough on its own, but it is important to be able to attract citizens to public open spaces and moreover to public services (i.e. this can also be called as a kind of invitation) and to integrate citizens from different origins and

with different social structures. Accordingly, it may be useful to address the concept of proximity in neighbourhood-scale planning discussions and/or practices with these dimensions. Therefore, our study extends the concept of ‘proximity’ to include users' motivations for using public spaces and their experiences in these spaces. However, it is also useful to note the risk that a study or project, or even a design, that only considers the concept of proximity may reduce urban planning to a single local dimension. Therefore, the importance of creating sustainable spaces should not be overshadowed when developing design proposals and in the planning process. Especially in urban peripheral areas, the sustainability context has to become increasingly important. Considering the two inevitable phenomena of increasing urban population and climate change impacts, these peri-urban areas have a more critical importance in the future of cities. Attention should be paid to ensuring the balance of both rural and urban elements they contain and to prioritizing approaches and even practices that will not cause environmental destruction.

1.1. Public Services as an Everyday Life Infrastructure

The accessibility of urban public infrastructure, equipment and services should be perceived as a service (Marchigiani and Bonfantini, 2022). Furthermore, the distribution of these services must be equitable, and planning derives its legitimacy from this justice and equality, with the role of the planner and planning in the public sector being to ensure equal access to public services, as well as the "just distribution (distributive justice)" of possibilities, opportunities, and development (Moroni, 2020; Moroni and De Franco, 2024). In this context, this study goes beyond a purely physical phenomenon of ‘equal/fair access to green spaces as the infrastructure of daily life’ and examines the motivations of users to prefer or not to prefer these spaces and their experiences in these spaces from an expanded perspective, first of all, by putting the concept of ‘proximity’ at an important point of the research, it is questioned how this can be achieved with a fair approach. This is because this study questions the possible reasons why public open spaces are not sufficiently preferred by users despite physical proximity and accessibility, and aims to relate this situation to urban design factors. In this context, one of the main arguments of the study is that, despite adequate physical facilities, some parks do not have enough inviting, integrate and inclusion qualities due to design deficiencies.

Therefore, the appropriate design of green spaces as part of the infrastructure of daily life can significantly improve the quality of life of neighbourhoods by positively affecting the visual, physical and psychological experiences of urban residents (Kahouei, 2013). European policies emphasise the critical role of cities in creating greener and fairer urban living spaces (Marchigiani and Bonfantini, 2022). Taking on this important role, cities focus on the goal of sustainability in cooperation with planners, architects and other relevant actors. While spatial organisation is being re-evaluated from this perspective, the provision of public services, which constitute the infrastructure of daily life, at the closest level to citizens – emphasizing not only geographical access but also the quality and inviting nature of these services – is of particular importance in order to create better living conditions, and this is the basis of the concept of ‘proximity’ (Valentine, 2013; Bricocoli et al., 2022). In particular, the importance of these services should be considered more sensitively in peri-urban areas, which can be more **socially and environmentally fragile**. For example, the role of public spaces around schools is important in this context because they are important places for students and families to socialise, gather and play, and their regulation and safety are considered part of public services (Bricocoli et al., 2022). The fact that public green spaces can be as important as schools when considered as the infrastructure of daily life, and even the Covid-19

pandemic has inevitably reminded everyone of the need for open public green spaces and the importance of accessibility to them.

At the same time, these public spaces (i.e. green spaces) are places where 'micro-publics' (sports clubs, music groups, community gardens, etc.) are important where different social groups come together and learn new forms of relationships with each other, as Amin (2014) states. Such spaces offer opportunities to improve intercultural understanding. Public spaces are known to be places of meeting, mingling and developing relationships, while prejudices are often associated with social and economic conditions (Valentine, 2010; 2020). Infrastructures are not just things, systems or outputs, but also complex social and technological processes that enable or hinder certain actions in the city (Graham and McFarlane, 2014). Therefore, the study of infrastructures is to examine the technologies and techniques through which the visible and invisible are separated, connected and managed in the social life of urban life. Infrastructure is an important site for the production of everyday life in the city. People make the city liveable by developing "relational infrastructures". These relationships enable the circulation of resources, information and emotions, and are a means of mobilising and creating opportunities within the complexity of urban life. In conclusion, infrastructures are an integral part of urban life and play a critical role in shaping the future of cities; moreover, they are an integral part of everyday life.

While the study focuses on urban green spaces, another central concept underpinning the research is the notion of 'egalitarian urban green spaces as infrastructure for daily life', which is scrutinised immediately after the notion of 'proximity'. In this context, it is considered as an analytical imperative that urban green spaces established with an egalitarian approach should be accessible and inviting to all urban residents with heterogeneous cultural and socio-economic strata located around them. Therefore, in this research, while focusing on green spaces as an indispensable element of the infrastructure of daily life, it is hypothesised that social inclusiveness is at least as decisive a factor as physical accessibility. It is thought that the design qualities of spaces can significantly affect their functionality, and it is predicted that designs that are disconnected from their context or alien to the environmental texture may lose their utilisation potential and even carry the risk of becoming idle over time. Therefore, it is argued that systematic consideration of conceptual frameworks such as intensification, invitingness and integration in the planning and design processes of urban public green spaces is vital for creating sustainable, environmentally sensitive and functional public spaces.

1.2. Peri-Urban Areas and Public Services

Due to phenomena such as population growth and migration, a dynamic urbanisation is taking place in cities that transcends traditional boundaries and reaches the surrounding regions. This process leads to a physical, morphological, sociodemographic, cultural, economic and functional transformation in the urban sectors (Barbosa et al., 2022). With increasing land prices in urban centres and rising living standards, people are looking for low population density areas in more suitable natural environments, which brings peri-urban areas to the forefront as an alternative to urban sprawl.

However, the important point here is 'should the peri-urban area have a character closer to agricultural activity or should it be a place where urban functions and urban sub-parts are produced?'. This questioning can broaden the perspective on peri-urban areas and lead to the development of sensitive approaches, which will

undoubtedly strengthen the prediction that peri-urban areas will become more important places in the future. The development of peri-urban landscapes therefore requires the delivery of new infrastructure and public services to these areas, helping them to develop economically and socially and integrate with cities (Sharma et al., 2023). However, as unplanned and uncontrolled development can lead to problems, it is of great importance to manage and plan these areas in a sustainable way (Barbosa et al., 2022).

In this direction, the fact that a large part of the world's population lives in urban areas brings about high population density in urban centres and the spatial concentration associated with this density. This situation causes urban public services and infrastructure facilities to be largely focused in city centres, thus leading to significant spatial inequalities in access to basic services in peri-urban areas. The concept of ‘proximity through accessibility’ is an important factor in urban planning (Armondi et al., 2022). This concept refers to the provision of access to services and infrastructures that are essential for daily life in a geographical and social context. Open green spaces, and schools in particular, are among these essential services and play a critical role for the social inclusion of the inhabitants of peri-urban areas (Bricocoli et al., 2022).

In the case of Milan, this study emphasises the importance of taking a systematic perspective of the city by examining public open spaces and the pedestrian facilities around them, and schools - which includes not only school buildings as structures but also school spaces and their environs. Public services in peri-urban areas are of great importance for sustaining social life, improving quality of life, the efficiency of transport systems and the integrity of urban planning (Renzoni, 2021; Pileri et al., 2022). In this context, it would be quite appropriate to consider the future of these areas from a planning perspective, as urban fringes have become so important and socially vulnerable - one might even say fragile - today. The fact that the study takes the peri-urban area as a case study and analyses it is a unique study in the context of the changes and unique characteristics of these areas. Urban growth creates rapidly changing environments, leading to adaptation or maladaptation (Lambert et al., 2021; Miles et al., 2021).

In the face of these changes, planning has a major role in addressing social participation and community belonging, as well as rethinking urban fringes with an equitable and just approach and strengthening cultural as well as social memory to carry these areas into the future. Peri-urban life is characterised by economic changes, social segregation, urban sprawl and various spatial innovations (Woltjer, 2014). While agricultural activities continue, residential development also occurs. Changes in peri-urban areas are driven by global capital decisions and various land use demands. These regions are the places where the transformation from rural to urban areas takes place. In this context, the participation of local actors in the management of urban periphery is actually quite valuable. In addition, the management of peri-urban areas is also shaped by institutional factors such as the capacity of local governments, lack of interregional coordination and the influence of the private sector (Sahana et al., 2023). To broaden the definition from a multifaceted perspective, peri-urban areas can be defined as areas that are **socially-economically active**, but outside the administrative or planning control of urban local governments and within the sphere of influence of the adjacent metropolis (Sharma et al., 2023).

Social vulnerabilities in peri-urban areas are related to a variety of factors arising from the complex structure of these areas. Heterogeneity of social groups, coexistence of communities with different interests, institutional fragmentation and poor governance weakens social cohesion in these areas. Land speculation and informal

economic activities have a negative impact on the living conditions of the poor, deepening social injustices. The loss of urban and rural characteristics reduces the quality of life of those living in these areas and increases their vulnerability. Moreover, ignoring the needs of marginalised groups within society and increasing socio-economic inequalities due to political factors further accentuate vulnerabilities in peri-urban areas. Therefore, sustainable management of these areas requires taking these vulnerabilities into account and developing strategies to ensure the participation of all stakeholders (Iaquinta and Drescher, 2000; Allen, 2003; Lambert et al., 2021; Barbosa et al., 2022).

1.3. Southern Margins of Milano

As a case study, this research analyses urban margins in the south of Milan, a large Italian metropolitan city. These areas are located both inside and outside the municipal boundaries and offer a unique context in which various urban elements coexist. From the perspective of ‘proximity’ in this **heterogeneous landscape**, how can a more equitable approach to access to public spaces in peri-urban areas be achieved and what urban design proposals can be developed? This question has been taken as the basis of the research. In this context, it analyses the access to green spaces, one of the cornerstones of urban public services, in the southern margins of Milan through the lens of ‘proximity’. It analyses the importance of urban sustainability and the importance of reconsidering public services with an equitable approach, and even the role of public green spaces **as an infrastructure of daily life** in these urban peripheries. It then analyses the study area through macro and microscale spatial analyses and presents an assessment that incorporates many features of urban design. In addition, it proposes a method based on interviews with citizens who use public green spaces during fieldwork. In this way, it reconsiders public green spaces and their surroundings in the context of many different public services and uses, land use diversity and urban margins with different criteria such as comfort and accessibility. It proposes a holistic methodology at macro and micro scales, including quantitative and qualitative urban design factors. Together with this methodology, the evaluation provides the basis for proposals that can adopt an inclusive, just and equitable approach to the urban margins of Milan. The findings of this research show that some parks are more accessible in terms of proximity to public services and users, while others are not used due to inadequate access. At the same time, it has been observed that the wounds of social segregation and community belonging are increasing. In this context, the study reveals its originality by evaluating ‘proximity’ not only as a physical phenomenon but also as a social phenomenon. Throughout the study, the **social and environmental fragility** of the southern fringes of Milan was never ignored, and the question of how can a more ‘anti-fragile’ peri-urban landscape be created? The question has also guided the process at many points. The research analysed in detail the reasons for the findings and problems identified in line with urban design principles and revealed the key role of the design of public green spaces. As a result, it aims to develop design proposals for the solution of the ‘proximity’ problem experienced in the access to public spaces where citizens living in urban peripheries can spend most of their daily lives.

In six chapters, this study analyses the concept of proximity in the urban environment and other notions directly or indirectly related to it, public green spaces with both quantitative and qualitative indicators. The first part of the study defines the key concepts, provides information about the study situation, as well as the position of the study in the general context of the contemporary literature, the expected results and the aim of the study. The

second chapter focuses on the methodology of the study, describing in detail the indicators and spatial analyses. the third chapter focuses on the study of the southern edge of Milan. The fourth section focuses on the results of the analyses and evaluations in the study and the general implications of these results. In the fifth section, the results and the local context are taken into consideration and strategies, pilot project interventions and the urban design proposals are explained. The last chapter presents the empirical conclusions that can be drawn from the research, their interpretation and contributions to future studies.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study aims to comprehensively examine the effects of urban design on the concept of ‘proximity’ and its role on equity of access to public green spaces and user experiences in peri-urban areas. The main objective is to develop urban design proposals that will ensure equal and quality access to public green spaces in peri-urban areas, taking into account not only physical accessibility but also design-oriented factors such as inviting, integration and inclusiveness. The research employs qualitative and quantitative methods based on literature review, field study, GIS (Geographic Information Systems)-based spatial analyses, archival research related to the study area, as well as the use of articles, lecture notes, reports, newspapers, and news sources, along with interviews conducted with the local inhabitants. The study was approached at macro and micro scales and analyses were conducted at different levels in the determined study area. The designated study area, Milan’s Southern Margins, has been examined at these two different scales, and as stated in Table 1, a total of 8 indicators have been identified and analysed at both macro and micro scales to understand the spatial **problems and potentials** within the scope of the study's objective. Subsequently, sub-indicators were determined for each indicator, and the methods to be used were defined. In line with the determined method, the study area was first examined at the macro scale (district level) using the existing condition mapping method to understand the area and identify public spaces and accessibility from a proximity perspective. In the light of the indicators determined here, the spatial characteristics of the area were defined as guiding and included in the methodology as indicators; Mobility, Green Areas, Public Services and Spatial Functionality were analysed. At the micro scale (Street-Block scale), public green spaces, which are one of the cornerstones of public spaces, were focussed on, and the current conditions of these spaces in terms of accessibility were examined in detail. Direct observation and interviews with the users of the parks at different times provided important inputs in the method of identifying the problematic area where urban design proposals could be implemented. In this study, the micro-scale analysis of public green spaces was evaluated through the lens of urban design principles, and these were determined as Accessibility, Attractiveness, Safety and Green Infrastructure. Within the study area, although the access potential is high, a problematic park area has been identified due to the lack of qualified equipment to attract users and the inadequacy of connections and directions to support access to the park. In order to overcome these problems, the study was finalised by developing design elements that will increase the functionality of the park and urban design proposals that will strengthen its physical and visual connections with its surroundings. Additionally, mapping, conceptual diagram representation, photographic techniques, and the matrix method were utilized for both scale analyses.

In this context, the indicators examined at **macro and micro scales** within the analysis framework determined in the study play a critical role in determining and understanding not only spatial inequalities but also other

restrictive elements such as functionality, safety and attractiveness in accessing public spaces in the context of urban design proposals. Each indicator is discussed below with its sub-indicators and their contributions to the methodological process are explained.

Table 1: Indicators of public green spaces by proximity from equitable perspective. References from the literature on these indicators, research tools for data collection and spatial analysis (Own Elaboration)

	INDICATORS	SUB-INDICATORS	METHODS/ANALYSIS	REFERENCES
A. MACRO SCALE	<i>a. Mobility</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The existence of roads of different degrees Existence of transportation modes/stops Accessibility to public green areas Accessibility to other facilities Availability of alternative roads by walking, cycling, wheelchair 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping of public transportation networks and stops Isochrone analysis (by walking for 5 and 10 mins) Mapping of pedestrian network and alternative modes 	Dias (2023), Sadushi (2023), Laan & Piersma (2021), Blečić, Saiu & Trunfio (2020), Jacobs (1995), Lotfi & Koohsari (2009).
	<i>b. Green Areas</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The existence of public parks Natural landscape Presence of greenery surfaces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping of public parks Mapping natural landscape Analyzing of permeable surfaces GIS based green density analysis 	Marino (2024), Scheiber (2021), Rasidi, Jamirsah & Said (2012), Gupta, K., Kumar, Pathan & Sharma (2012).
	<i>c. Public Services</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The existence of public services (primary school, kindergarten, parish) Availability of recreational facilities and public open spaces Land use (mixed-use places) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land-use analysis Mapping of open space system and recreational facilities Spatial analysis of amenities 	Bricocoli, Renzoni & Savoldi (2022), Breuste & Artmann (2020), Belge & Ercan (2022), Gehl (2013), Jacobs (1995)
	<i>d. Spatial Functionality</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of land use User groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land-use map and analysis Mapping of population density Analyzing of age distribution of users Variety, diversity and vitality of functions 	Rasheed & Mahmoud (2024), Jiang & Gao (2024)
B. MICRO SCALE	<i>a. Accessibility</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Access to alternative transportation modes Walkability Index (API) Existence of public transportation stops (in 5 min) Presence of fences/barriers of public parks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping of public transportation networks and stops Evaluation of the walkability index of the pedestrian path within each park Analyzing of fences and barriers of parks entrances 	Frank, Sallis, Saelens, Leary, Cain, Conway & Hess (2010) Smith (2023), Laan & Piersma (2021), Ercan & Belge (2020)
	<i>b. Attractiveness</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of landuse Proximity to services (schools, kindergarten, parish, commercial) Attractive features (equipments in parks) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land-use analysis Mapping of services located within a 5-minute walk of the park Analyzing of elements 	Mulliner, Maliene (2011), Giles-Corti, Broomhall, Knuiaman, Collins, Douglas & Donovan (2005), Gehl (2013)
	<i>c. Safety</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Feel Lightning Maintenance and cleanliness of parks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping lighting of parks Analyzing maintenance and cleanliness of parks Direct observations 	Bedimo-Rung, Mowen & Cohen (2005), Ercan & Belge (2020), Jacobs (1995)
	<i>d. Green Infrastructure</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Vegetation typologies Waterbodies Forestry Permeable/unpermeable surfaces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyzing of vegetation typologies for each parks Mapping of ecological opportunities Detection and calculation of permeable surfaces based on GIS 	Shu-Yang, Freedman & Cote (2004), Givoni, B. (1991), Halecki, Stachura, Fudała, Stec, & Kuboń (2023)

2.1. Mobility

In urban planning, accessibility is a fundamental element that enables city residents to reach all kinds of spaces they need -such as parks, streets, public buildings, green areas, and other public spaces- comfortably and without barriers. This accessibility is supported by an effective urban mobility system and various transportation options, including public transit, bicycles, pedestrians, and private vehicles, while requiring a series of planning, design, and infrastructure efforts. In line with this study, accessibility to green spaces is a concept that measures how available and reachable green areas are within certain distances (Laan and Piersma, 2021). On the other hand, it can also be characterized as an indicator of **urban quality of life**. From a ‘proximity’ perspective, as seen in approaches like the 15-minute city model, green spaces are considered a fundamental need, and it is emphasized that these areas should be close to the homes of urban residents (Dias, 2023). In line with this research, the concept of mobility, as shown in Table 1, examines the identified sub-indicators. Different road classifications within the study area were mapped, and the level of access to public spaces in this region was analysed in the context of urban mobility, focusing on how transportation is carried out and mapping various transportation types and stops. The crucial point here is the access of local inhabitants, primarily through public transportation and walking. In this regard, considering physical proximity, an isochrone analysis was conducted using QGIS to identify areas reachable within a maximum of 5 to 10 minutes on foot from public parks in the study area, thereby determining other accessible facilities (Sadushi, 2023). Additionally, numerous articles and theses were referenced during the research, and the connection of the study's criteria to the literature, as well as its position within the literature, were detailed. Therefore, the analyses conducted based on the indicators specified in Table 1 demonstrate that the equitable and sufficient distribution of green spaces within accessible distances plays a significant role in enhancing people's quality of life.

2.2. Green Areas

Green areas are classified as parks, gardens, recreational areas, natural vegetation, woodland, etc. and are an integral part of an urban area (Gupta et al., 2012). The proximity, accessibility and equal distribution of green areas are of great importance to increase the quality of life of urban residents (Scheiber, 2021). In line with this research, a quantitative method-based analysis was conducted and mapped to primarily examine the presence and distribution of green spaces within the study area (Table 1). Urban green spaces play a critical role not only in ensuring environmental quality but also in maintaining sustainability as permeable surface areas within the city (Marino, 2024). Therefore, the surfaces of green spaces were also considered as a sub-indicator, contributing to the research through GIS-based analysis by examining the presence of permeable surfaces. On the other hand, we can discuss the inclusive role of green spaces. These areas are favourable spaces for promoting social interaction and function as everyday living spaces (Rasidi et al., 2012). In conclusion, proximity to green areas is a critical point in this research, demonstrating the importance of integrating green spaces, their accessibility, and quality in urban planning and design processes.

2.3. Public Services

Public services and spaces, another essential component of urban daily life, are categorized into various groups, similar to green spaces. These include education, health, transportation, social services, and other facilities where people spend a significant portion of their daily lives. They can be defined as 'everyday infrastructures' (Pileri et al, 2022). Therefore, public spaces must be equally accessible to everyone (Belge and Ercan, 2022). In

line with this research, public services were limited within the scope of the study by determining their sub-indicators. In this context, public services in the study area were determined through land use mapping and focused on these categories. In the micro-scale part of the study method, analyses were carried out on educational services and open public spaces concentrated in the spatial environment, providing input to emphasize the connection with public green spaces in particular. Consequently, public spaces should be designed as accessible and integrated systems that meet people's daily needs (Gehl, 2013).

2.4. Spatial Functionality

As shown in Table 1 prepared within the context of the study method, the final indicator of the macro-scale section—spatial functionality—and its sub-indicators have been determined. Spatial functionality is defined as an indicator that analyses both social and spatial dimensions by considering the life within the boundaries of the study area in a holistic manner. Within this framework, the analysis focused on mapping all land uses, examining their diversity, and conducting a profile analysis of user groups. The coexistence of different land uses enhances the efficiency and vitality of the urban system (Rasheed and Mahmoud, 2024). Understanding the role of spatial usage in the daily life cycle of communities contributes to social harmony, adopting a social cohesion approach in design, rather than solely focusing on spatial integrity (Jiang and Gao, 2024). Consequently, this guides the study with findings that reveal where and why spatial uses and preferences are concentrated, particularly in the functioning of urban daily life.

2.5. Accessibility

Accessibility is addressed as an indicator in the micro-scale section of the method table (Table 1), and its sub-indicators have been determined accordingly. The aim here is to measure the accessibility of parks within the study area from a micro-scale perspective, based on different criteria. In line with the research, the following factors have been identified as critical criteria for analysing park accessibility: the diversity of transportation modes available to access the designated parks, pedestrian pathways, stops within walking distance, the walkability index, and the presence of fences/barriers surrounding the parks from a design perspective. Because fences / barriers are also elements that restrict access and provide an idea about the perception of the use of parks (Smith, 2023). The study, approached through a proximity lens, emphasizes the necessity of ensuring access to parks, particularly for pedestrians. At this point, it was examined whether users can access these parks on foot from parks, living spaces or other public spaces, and the increasingly important issue of planning and design, walkability, was taken into account (Ercan and Belge, 2020). Therefore, accessibility is not limited to physical distance or geographical proximity; it is discussed as a phenomenon shaped by micro-scale dynamics such as the quality of pedestrian infrastructure, the presence of obstructive design elements, and integration between transportation modes.

2.6. Attractiveness

Making areas attractive is as crucial as ensuring their accessibility and has a vital impact (Moura et al., 2017). Thus, good urban design can enhance the appeal of these spaces (Mulliner and Maliene, 2011). Therefore, the

micro-scale section of the study emphasizes not only parks themselves but also the diversity and mixed land uses within and around the parks in terms of attractiveness. This is also a critical factor influencing the intensity of use in these areas, as attractiveness contributes to their overall functionality (Giles-Corti et al., 2005). In this context, different service uses that can be reached by walking from the parks have been mapped and an analysis of different equipment, which is another element that can provide attractiveness for people in parks, has been provided.

2.7. Safety

According to Jacobs (1995), urban safety is achieved not through monotonous, single-use, or underutilized spaces but through vibrant streets, mixed land uses, and the presence of "eyes on the street." From a holistic perspective, when attractiveness and accessibility as discussed in previous sections are ensured, a sense of safety can also be fostered for user groups. Within this framework, safety is evaluated as an indicator for the parks analysed in this study. At the micro-scale, safety in parks is assessed through physical factors (e.g., the presence of lighting, maintenance, and cleanliness) and perceptual factors derived from direct observations and interviews conducted with park users during fieldwork for each park in the study area (Ercan and Belge, 2020). In this context, safety is considered a multidimensional criterion, highlighting the necessity of integrated urban design proposals.

2.8. Green Infrastructure

Parks can be considered one of the components of green infrastructure. Green spaces, including parks, are areas with high ecological potential (Halecki et al., 2023). Therefore, parks and urban green spaces provide environmental benefits to cities and can serve as practical areas that embrace ecological design approaches (Shu-Yang et al., 2004). At this point, the last indicator addressed within the scope of micro-scale analyses is green infrastructure. Sub-indicators include vegetation typologies within parks, the presence and ratio of permeable and impermeable surfaces, and natural features such as water bodies and forestry opportunities. In line with this, analyses supporting the study's objectives have been conducted, contributing an ecological perspective to the research. These findings play a significant role in shaping the urban design proposals presented in the later sections of this study.

3. CASE STUDY: SOUTHERN MARGINS OF MILANO (*STADERA, CHIESA ROSSA, MISSAGLIA AND GRATOSOGLIO*)

Milan, located in the heart of the Lombardy region, is Italy's second-largest metropolitan city in terms of population density. Initially an industrial hub, Milan has evolved into the centre of a metropolitan area with a population exceeding seven million (OECD, 2006). This expansion has reinforced the city's polycentric structure and enhanced its interaction with surrounding urban areas (Balducci et al., 2017; Albrechts et al., 2017). Three main elements of road dependency that shape regional urbanization dynamics in and around Milan can be identified (De Vidovich and Scolari, 2022). Historically, these factors have enabled Milan to develop a polycentric structure and thereby interact with surrounding cities. Furthermore, it has been observed that Milan's radial

growth pattern has blurred the boundaries between urban and suburban areas (Figure 1a) (De Vidovich and Scolari, 2022). Particularly, suburban settlements (Figure 1b) built between the 1950s and 1970s are undergoing significant transformations, necessitating a redefinition of their identity. In this context, the proximity project is addressed in the urban periphery, starting from the role of neighbourhoods. Neighbourhoods can be characterized by the urban subdivisions they produce and the social context of the citizens they house. The urban fabric of the region includes a number of public housing neighbourhoods built in the mid-20th century (Figure 1c). These neighbourhoods are characterized by large green areas, public spaces, and social amenities that reflect the social housing policies and urban planning approaches of the period. The study area is located along one of the radial roads extending from *Porta Ticinese* towards Rozzano and Pavia, following Via dei Missaglia, a major transportation corridor connecting the area to the metropolitan region (Figure 1d). This corridor, supported by metro, tram lines (3 and 15), and bus routes, facilitates access to the city centre and surrounding settlements.

Figure 1: Milano Urban Area and Surroundings (a), Public Housing in Milano (b), Shows Public Housing Buildings Years (c), Milano Accessibility Map: Underground Lines and Tram (d). (Reproduced by Authors Using the Master Plans Studio’s Materials, UPPD, 2023-2024)

South Milan can be considered as a laboratory of innovative ideas and design solutions for housing and public spaces. The area is equipped with important public services such as schools, playgrounds, sports facilities and cultural centres, which we can call ‘daily life infrastructure’. This infrastructure facilitates the daily life of the inhabitants and encourages social interaction. However, this area is not only of historical and planning significance, but also of contemporary urban problems and potentials. Built in the mid-20th century, these residential neighbourhoods need to adapt to changing social, economic and environmental conditions over time. This large area of South Milan is both socially and environmentally fragile. This fragility stems from the historical development, socio-economic structure and environmental conditions of the area. Built in the mid-20th century (Figure 1b and c), the public housing neighbourhoods were initially designed to meet the need for social housing, but over time have faced various challenges due to changing demographics, economic conditions and social dynamics. An important aspect of this fragility is the visible loss of function in some of the originally planned commercial and social facilities in these neighbourhoods. Over the decades, shifts in economic activity and changing social needs have led to underutilisation or abandonment of certain buildings, resulting in a decline in the vitality and social cohesion of their immediate surroundings. These challenges can include issues such as social exclusion and rising crime rates. At the same time, the region is also environmentally fragile. The area is surrounded by the *Parco Agricolo Sud Milano* (Figure 2), an important environmental and productive system. However, the area has a fragile structure due to housing pressure and insufficient sensitivity to green spaces. As it is a peri-urban area, it contains both urban and rural elements, but increasing pressure risks making the area denser in terms of urban elements in the future. In today's urban landscapes, especially in the face of climate change, the role of urban fringes and suburban areas is undergoing a significant transformation (Aşıcı, 2023). These areas have started to gain importance as they will form the growth axes of the cities of the future. When considered in this context, the case study has many features of the surrounding agricultural park and the many natural landscapes and rural areas within it, and has important natural resources and biodiversity (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Green System of Milano (Reproduced by Authors Using the Master Plans Studio's Materials, UPPD, 2023-2024)

Figure 3: Google Earth Views of Milan's Southern Margins: Stadera (a), Chiesa Rossa (b), Missaglia (c), and Gratosoglio (d) (Produced by the authors using Google Earth satellite imagery base)

Within the case study of this research, there are settlements with different names: Stadera built in 1920s (Figure 3a), Chiesa Rossa built in 1960-66 (Figure 3b), Missaglia built in 1968-72 (Figure 3c), and Gratosoglio built in 1963-71 (Figure 3d). These urban fringe settlements provide intriguing case studies in terms of urban planning and social dynamics. As a reflection of the complex urban structure of Milan's southern periphery, these four neighbourhoods offer valuable insights into issues such as social inequality and the role of public spaces. Lastly, it is important to note that, as in many other public housing neighbourhoods, this part of the city has a high number of well-distributed public facilities, including schools, kindergartens, churches, community centres, municipal offices, and sports facilities represent an important resource that has **gradually lost its leading role** over the years. The loss of this leading role of public facilities is often accompanied by a decline in their physical

condition and functionality, further contributing to the social and spatial fragility of neighbourhoods. Under-utilisation or abandonment of these structures can create dead zones, affect perceived safety and social interaction in the public realm, and prevent the “infrastructure of everyday life” from functioning effectively.

3.1. Macro Scale Analysis

As a result of the macro-scale assessments, analyses were carried out in the context of four main indicators (Mobility, Green Spaces, Public Services and Spatial Functionality) throughout the study area (Figure 4). Via dei Missaglia (Figure 4a), which provides direct access and connection of the area with the city centre, stands out as an important element of the transport infrastructure in the region. Roads of varying grades to the east and west of the site are functional both in terms of services and general accessibility. The presence of two different tram lines (Figure 4a) ensures the accessibility of the area both externally and internally. These lines run from the southern periphery of the city to the Duomo Cathedral, the most important historical and cultural focal point.

Figure 4: Macro Scale Analysis Mapping: Mobility Analysis with Merged Isochrone (5 min. and 10 min. by walking) and Public Transportation mapping (a), Green System analysis with Green Classification (b), Isochrone analysis 5 min. by walking with Public Services (c), Synthesis Map with Authors' interpretation (d). (Own Elaboration) (Source: Census Data, ISTAT, Geoportale Lombardia, DUSAF 7, OSM)

The study area, located in the southern periphery of Milan, is home to different connecting roads and internal service roads. In the Stadera area, the grid pattern of interconnecting roads connecting to the main road is noteworthy. As you move towards the south, the design, geometry and function of the internal service roads change with the unique design of the public housing settlements. The fact that the roads in these areas are located on the periphery of the city causes them to have a vehicle-oriented structure and there are no bicycle paths except for a limited linear area. This makes it difficult for residents to use sustainable means of transport. On the other hand, the presence of roads of different grades and the absence of traffic congestion during working hours, except for the main street *Via dei Missaglia*, can be considered as a characteristic feature of the urban

periphery. In addition, the low population density of the area has a positive effect on this situation. All settlements in the area are adequately served by public transport infrastructure (Figure 4a). Although tram access in particular provides a good connection from the outside, the process of travelling from tram stops to residences can be challenging. The isochrone analysis (Figure 4a and 4c), which measures accessibility to green spaces, shows that the spatial distribution of public green spaces is favourable. Accessibility to public green spaces on foot is a valuable advantage for residents. The isochrone analysis analysing 5-10-minute walking distances (Figures 4a and 4c) confirms that pedestrian accessibility is positive. On a macro scale, access to other services such as sports facilities is also adequate. The location of the metro stop (*Abbiategrosso*) and tram stops contribute significantly to mobility.

Figure 5: Green Area Size Map (a), Population Map (b). (Own Elaboration) (Source: Census Data, ISTAT, Geoportale Lombardia)

The case area has a significant character with the presence of public green areas. The distribution of public green spaces and the classification of the different green spaces (Figure 4b) clearly shows that the area is surrounded by natural landscape and that this landscape has the potential to be an ecological corridor moving towards the interior of the study area. The amount and distribution of permeable surfaces (including public spaces) is also quite high (Figure 4b). The combination of water and natural landscape, especially along the *Naviglio* canal, creates an important natural texture. However, the lack of proper management of this natural landscape and

the old pedestrian facilities around it, and the fact that some points remain idle, creates a sense of abandonment. Nevertheless, these areas offer potential for adaptive uses.

The green area size analysis (Figure 5a) was conducted using QGIS based on data at two different spatial scales to measure the quantity of green areas in square meters. The results indicate that within the administrative boundaries of Milan, the amount of green space ranges between 10,000 m² and 1,500,000 m², highlighting that a significant portion of the area consists of permeable surfaces. Within the study area boundaries, the distribution of green space appears relatively balanced in terms of size. To evaluate this data in relation to population, Figure 5b presents the population count within each census tract, revealing a range between 1 and 500 inhabitants within the study area. When these two datasets—green space size and population distribution—are considered together, the findings suggest that although the quantity of green space may be sufficient in absolute terms, there is a critical deficiency in its spatial distribution and accessibility, which warrants further reconsideration.

When public services are examined, it is observed that schools, kindergartens, churches, community centres, and sports facilities are distributed in a number and balanced manner consistent with the established planning standards (PGT) in the area (Figure 4d). However, although the presence of these facilities is a positive indicator, the fact that they have started to lose their functions over time is a problematic situation when considered in the context of ‘public infrastructure of daily life’. However, from a qualitative point of view, this loss of function further increases the fragility of an already socially fragile area. Schools should be evaluated not only as buildings, but also in terms of the open spaces and social opportunities they offer (Bricocoli et al., 2022). The presence of recreational spaces adds a positive value to the area; however, direct observations show that these spaces are underutilised, even during the busiest hours on the streets. As confirmed in the interviews, people usually prefer recreation areas outside the area by car or public transport. These observations and interviews reveal that although public open spaces are quantitatively sufficient, there are various problems when evaluated with a citizen-oriented approach. Due to the peri-urban characteristic of the area, the lack of mixed uses and the absence of various activities other than basic commercial activities (markets, small shops, etc.) reduce human mobility both around public spaces and on the streets. This situation causes the streets, which are natural socialising areas, to fail to fulfil their function. The absence of mixed use in the entire area can be considered natural; however, the presence of such activities around public open spaces is important. The lack of maintenance and regular control of the facilities in public spaces cause these facilities to lose their importance and lead to unequal distribution of services.

The study area is dominated by limited mixed uses and is characterised by a dense residential fabric. Despite the presence of schools, kindergartens and churches, which offer important venues for social interaction, this potential is limited by the fact that sports facilities are often privately owned or lack sufficient public open space, as can be seen in Figure 4d (see Section 3.2). The lack of diversity of use in the region also leads to a lack of services catering to different user groups. This has a negative impact on the search for diversity in parks and their surroundings for user groups in the census tracts whose population densities are shown in Figure 5b. The age distribution analysis carried out to understand the demographic structure of the user groups revealed that 46% of the inhabitants are adults aged 50 and over. Other age groups are distributed as 10% (0-11 years), 8% (12-18 years), 17% (19-35 years) and 20% (36-50 years). Considering this demographic structure, it is seen that the public green spaces in the region have difficulty in attracting different user groups in terms of function. In terms of design, there are no uses that will bring different groups together or enable them to spend time in the parks. As a result, the parks, which are insufficient to offer various opportunities such as sports, recreation, commercial and community activities, cannot attract local users under the current conditions.

3.2. Micro Scale Analysis

At the micro scale, accessibility, attractiveness, safety and green infrastructure indicators that directly affect the user experience of the study area were analysed. This analysis aims to reveal the current potential of the area and the problems encountered.

Figure 6: Micro Scale Analysis. Catalogue: Way to Dive into Park Exploration and Matrix: regarding to parks with set of criteria (Own Elaboration)

The accessibility analyses identified the specific potentials and problems of the ten parks in the study area. The presence of artificial boundaries (fences) restricting access to the parks was observed. The catalogue presented in Figure 6 was created as a result of a detailed examination of the parks using the visual method. While creating the catalogue, this catalogue, which was created by using various angles in order to ensure that the parks are perceived simultaneously with other parks, acts as an abacus. This catalogue shows that the park with the highest accessibility potential is park number 9. The fact that this park is within walking distance to the tram stop and that the streets examined within the scope of the IAPI index (Inclusive Accessibility by Proximity, a study conducted by the research group of Politecnico di Milano) have a moderate level of walkability positively affect the accessibility of the park. However, user experiences show that the perceived walkability of these streets is

low. During direct observations, ground floor uses that are not open especially in the evenings and ground floors that have been empty for a long time negatively affect perceived safety in this context. The user experience was understood in the context of the answers to the question 'Would you feel safer if there were more commercial activities or more people in the parks and streets?'.

Returning to the physical elements of the parks, park number 9 has no fence and this offers important potentials in terms of both access and design. As seen in the matrix in Figure 6, the park has problems such as "isolated", "unsafe" and "neglected". Proximity to public services may not directly increase the attractiveness of the park, but it has the potential to engage local people in the parks. If it is accepted that the attractiveness of parks is provided by good design, in this context, in order for the park to attract users, it needs innovative and environmentally sensitive designs and proposals that do not increase current problems and risks, but adopt and overcome them. Another important aspect is that the park should be located in an integrated system with public services, so that the circulation that can make the parks more active areas can be provided in an integrated system, and this integration is important in the Italian case, where the use of parks through schools is intensive and familiar. All parks were analysed in this context and it was seen that most of the problems were caused by the lack of a specific function or equipment. In park 9, the lack of renewal and inadequate equipment prevents the park from attracting users (Figure 7). Parks that have the potential to serve different user groups face problems of management and lack of design. Sports equipment or areas that can host events that can bring users together do not provide adequate service. In terms of security, the problem of perceptual security comes to the fore in almost all parks. Interviews and feedback from different user groups indicate that the fact that parks are empty and make users feel unsafe is one of the biggest factors preventing park use. The lack of natural control mechanisms (where possible) prevents people from using parks. Parco della Pace (9) has potential in terms of its location and surrounding uses. The security problem can be improved if users are encouraged to spend time in this park.

Detailed vegetation analyses in ecological context revealed the presence of landscape features and local vegetation. This is important for the ecological cycle and green system. The presence of water (Figure 7), woodland from south to north and the concentration of native vegetation in part of the park provide positive ecological contributions to Park 9. In terms of ecological opportunities and spatial orientations, although two parks stand out in the south and centre of the area, park 9 stands out with its strategic and inclusive location. The amount of permeable surfaces has been analysed in detail and park designs have been evaluated in a way to address different surfaces as a whole. In park 3, some of the park uses, such as the library and open foyer area, consist of hard and impermeable surfaces (Figure 7). This situation is reflected in the parks as different benefits or problems. However, it should not be forgotten that problems can be evaluated as potentials when considered design-orientated.

Figure 7: Photos from Site Visit. (Çağlanur Kösel, 2024)

4. RESULTS

While the study area stands out with its transport infrastructure and green space potential at the macro scale, at the micro scale, the problems of accessibility and attractiveness of parks negatively affect the user experience. While *Parco della Pace* stands out with its location and ecological potential, its potential to establish a strong relationship with public services makes it stand out more than others. Other parks face management and design problems. Lack of equipment and perceived safety issues reduce their utilisation potential. User opinions reveal that the empty parks and the lack of natural control mechanisms increase security concerns. However, the ecological richness and strategic location of the parks can be potentially utilised through design-oriented approaches. The presence of native vegetation and the correct use of permeable surfaces are important for a sustainable urban environment. In the design of the parks, mixed use should be encouraged and equipment that will increase social interaction should be provided. In conclusion, user-oriented, sustainable and inclusive design strategies should be adopted in the urban planning of the area. Accessibility is not only related to physical proximity, but also to social and economic factors. Therefore, in addition to the equal distribution of public services, the unique needs of the peri-urban areas and the social, economic and experiential dimensions of proximity, which are not only physical phenomena, should also be taken into account. In line with the results of the analyses, design proposals that address the potentials and problems of the parks have been developed. These recommendations aim to create a green-oriented system that supports a multidimensional understanding of proximity through the strategies of **Intensification, Inviting and Integrating, Cohesion**, ensuring the equality of parks in the peri-urban area not only in terms of physical access, but also in terms of responsiveness to the needs of different user groups, safety and social participation opportunities.

5. DISCUSSION

As determined in the results part of the study, a design proposal has been developed based on the findings derived from the analyses, taking into account the identified problems and potentials of the selected parks. This design primarily focuses on ensuring that the public green spaces (i.e., parks) within this peri-urban study area are equitable, creating a green-oriented proximity system, and developing urban design proposals through the application of **Intensification, Inviting and Integrating, and Cohesion** strategies. The conceptual diagrams presented in Figure 8 below were used as a synthesis and transitional phase following the analyses to determine these strategies before formulating the design proposals.

Firstly, as seen in Figure 8a, the abandoned buildings surrounding the parks in the area have been identified as a potential opportunity. These buildings offer significant potential for developing diverse functions and creating a variety of uses (diversity of uses), particularly to enhance the intensity of park usage, attractiveness, and safety. On the other hand, Figure 8b incorporates pedestrian movements into the diagram, emphasizing the importance of ensuring pedestrian access and walkability. Here, the key point to note is the role of pedestrian pathways as connectors between parks and the pedestrians who enable this integration. Finally, in the system illustrated in Figure 8c, it is highlighted that the connections provided by pedestrian pathways between parks merge with the natural elements and ecological opportunities present in the study area and around the focal parks, thereby fostering an ecological approach in the design.

Figure 8: Conceptual Diagrams: Unveiling Strategies (Own Elaboration)

Intensification

The intensification strategy, which can also be defined as **widening the spectrum of use**, aims to increase the use of parks as a multifaceted and dynamic public space. In this context, offering activities that appeal to different age groups makes parks more inclusive and attractive. In addition, flexible design elements and portable furniture support a variety of uses and enable more effective use of the area. While social interaction is encouraged with various events (concerts, workshops, film screenings), alternative activities added to traditional sports areas (disc golf, slackline) diversify the use of parks. Thus, public green spaces become more intensive, accessible and sustainable.

Inviting and Integrating

The Inviting and Integrating strategy aims to enhance the identity of parks and make them safer for users. In this context, symbolic elements reflecting the character of the region should be incorporated to strengthen spatial belonging. Additionally, within the framework of proximity, the goal is to improve the user experience by establishing cohesive and guiding systems between parks. By increasing vibrancy along pedestrian pathways, the sense of security is reinforced, while abandoned areas are repurposed for diverse and varied uses. Thus, within an integrated system, parks become more accessible, inviting, and cohesive public spaces.

Cohesion

The Cohesion strategy aims to support parks with sustainable infrastructure solutions and strengthen ecological connections. Green infrastructure applications such as rain gardens and permeable surfaces increase the resilience of park ecosystems by improving water management. In addition, environmentally friendly services such as solar lighting, bicycle parks and water filling stations encourage park use. The existence of ecological

opportunities along pedestrian paths connecting parks and the creation of ecological corridors increase biodiversity by integrating parks with natural habitats. The reorganization of unused green areas with native vegetation supports habitats. These approaches ensure the proximity and integrated system of parks to themselves, while increasing ecological sustainability, making parks more resilient and interconnected.

Urban Design Proposals

In line with the strategies outlined in the previous sections, the area shown in Figure 9 has been selected as the pilot site for implementing urban design proposals, taking into account the problems and potentials identified in the study area. As can be seen in Figure 9, this area is called *Parco della Pace* and functions as a park but is not actively used. Among the other parks examined in the study area, this site was chosen as the most problematic yet highly potential design area. Regarding *Parco della Pace*, the findings from the analysis reveal that the park, located in a peri-urban area, faces issues such as neglected, secluded and safety concerns. On the other hand, the diverse uses surrounding the park (e.g., kindergarten, sports facilities, parks, etc.), abandoned structures, and ecological opportunities integrated with the nearby river make this area an inevitable focal point for applying the previously emphasized strategies of "Intensification, Inviting and Integrating, and Cohesion." In this context, the aim of the research is to reduce the physical problems in public spaces located in peri-urban areas, to eliminate the deficiencies between community and social connections, and to create public green spaces that function as everyday life infrastructure with urban design proposals that provide an equitable proximity for both people and other uses, as in the case of *Parco della Pace*.

Figure 9: Pilot Project Site and its Characteristics (Own Elaboration)

First of all, these urban design proposals mentioned, as seen in the Master Plan (Figure 10), are designed to consider not only the park, which is the main focal point of the pilot project area, but also its surroundings, embracing design principles that promote sustainability, inclusivity, and social cohesion. A holistic approach has been adopted in this design. During the design process, different focus areas within the pilot project zone were identified, and the design proposals were shaped according to these areas, guided by the established strategies.

Firstly, starting with the park as the main focal point of the design, this area has been designed to function as the central hub of the composite structure of parks within the study area, serving as a gathering point for local residents. The principles adopted during this design process are to make the park active, attractive, and walkable. These principles were determined due to the park's current idle state, lack of planned activities, and distance from essential amenities. In this regard, particular reference has been made to the Intensification and Inviting and Integrating strategies. The design aims to transform the park into an active space and a meeting point through elements such as appropriate equipment, children's play areas, accessible entrances for people with disabilities, walking paths, outdoor sports facilities, and community event spaces (e.g., an amphitheatre). On the other hand, in line with the Cohesion strategy, an artificial lake design proposal has been developed, embracing ecological and sustainable principles. This lake will function as a sponge to collect and manage rainwater while adding aesthetic value. This approach also supports the park's adaptation to environmental challenges.

Figure 10: Master Plan and Section N-S (Own Elaboration)

Other focal points, as seen in the pilot project area (Figure 9), consist of various uses around the park that interact with it and hold potential for the study's objectives. These include sports facilities, abandoned areas, and kindergartens. Integrating diverse sports initiatives into urban parks is crucial for the long-term health of the population. The master plan (Figure 10) proposes interventions to integrate these areas into public spaces, including privately owned sports facilities. Abandoned buildings are being transformed to increase activity, interaction and liveliness, guided by the principles of diversity, social mix and active use. The aim is to create an inclusive environment for people of different incomes, ethnicities, ages and abilities, and to directly increase park use. This is an intervention that will also directly affect the intensity of use of the park. Kindergartens, due to their proximity to urban parks, provide an opportunity to include schools in policy planning, adding importance to the urban design of the park.

Another focus, as evident from the strategies, is the creation of pedestrian zones (Figure 11), which play a key role in connecting parks and other uses from a proximity perspective. It also increases the use and value of these areas by allowing people to explore ecological corridors and connect with nature. Its basic principles are to adopt a walkable, green and human scale. Here, by pedestrianizing unused areas and areas located at connection points, they are transformed into functional and aesthetically pleasing areas where people walk, cycle and spend time in the urban environment. In this context, they are crucial in terms of comfort, safety and attractiveness.

Figure 11: Render of Pedestrian Zone Design (Own Elaboration)

Finally, the ecological zones, particularly addressed and designed in line with the Cohesion strategy, represent green corridors that symbolize the connections between parks through their role in the design. Their core principles are connectivity, compatibility with local ecology, and resilience. The goal is to adopt an approach based on the coexistence of all components in the area and to carry natural diversity into the future in a more sustainable structure. Ecological corridor design forms the foundation of this approach. The principle of local ecology involves planting trees, grasses, flowers and shrubs specific to Milan and to this region in particular, providing food, shelter and breeding grounds for wildlife. It aims to create corridors that allow pedestrian flows through ecological areas and also allow wildlife to pass. In this context, pedestrian bridges (Figure 12) play an important role. The pedestrian bridge designed here is a connecting element that acts as an ecological corridor and brings together nature and humans.

Figure 12: Render of Ecological Zone, Pedestrian Bridge Design (Own Elaboration)

As a result, the pilot project area identified in the South of Milan offers a comprehensive design framework that is holistic, inclusive, sustainable, and aims for social cohesion, in line with the defined vision. In accordance with the prepared Master Plan, the primary design focus, *Parco della Pace*, is intended to be transformed from a derelict state into a vibrant urban green space that serves both the community and nature. For the other focus areas, as mentioned above, different design principles have been adopted, and the urban design project for *Parco della Pace* aims to be a project that ensures equitable proximity for all.

6. CONCLUSION

This study addresses the inequalities in access to urban green spaces in the southern periphery of Milan from a proximity perspective. The spatial analyses were conducted at macro and micro scales during the study, and the user interviews conducted during the field study revealed that the parks in the region exhibit significant differences in terms of accessibility, attractiveness, safety and green infrastructure. The findings show that the parks in the Milan-Sud are more accessible when the concept of proximity is considered, while the others are not used due to lack of facilities, safety problems and inadequate access. The study also identified the social segregation and weakening of community belonging as an indicator of the fragility of the periphery, and stated that this situation is due to the lack of public spaces. It is also emphasized here that proximity is not only a matter of spatial distance, but a multidimensional concept that integrates social, ecological and infrastructural dynamics. The findings demonstrate that peri-urban public green spaces (parks) can be made much more functional and accessible by combining cohesion, inviting and integrating, and intensification strategies in a comprehensive urban design approach. As stated in the research question, the concept of proximity in peri-urban areas and urban green spaces as an infrastructure for daily life offers significant contributions to the literature. It provides a comprehensive framework for future research to assess spatial inequalities in public space access and develop urban design proposals. As cities continue to grow, proximity remains a critical imperative to ensure accessibility to public spaces in urban environments and to achieve sustainable and socially just urban environments.

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APPENDIX: INTERVIEW QUESTION GUIDE AND MOTIVATION FOR INTERVIEWS

To gain a deeper understanding of users' perceptions and experiences related to urban parks in the study area, a series of semi-structured interviews were conducted during the site visit. These interviews were carried out with approximately 13 to 15 individuals who were either living in the area with different ages and actively using the parks at the time to explore the issues. The qualitative insights gathered from these interviews were instrumental in shaping the spatial analysis and informing the subsequent design proposals developed in the study.

Questions:

1. How frequently do you visit the park? What are the reasons preventing you from visiting more often? Additionally, among the parks in the study area, which one do you visit most frequently?
2. What is your perception of the maintenance level of the park?

3. Do you think the park offers a diverse range of experiences? Do you feel it is repetitive in nature, or are you able to access the services you expect?
4. Do you notice a difference in your sense of safety at different times of the day?
5. To what extent do you feel safe while spending time in the park? Do you notice a difference in your sense of safety at different times of the day?

Limitations: The one-to-one interviews conducted within the scope of the Master Plans Studio at Politecnico di Milano had limitations in terms of sample size due to time constraints within the scope of the course.

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All procedures followed were in accordance with the ethical standards. | Araştırma etik standartlara uygun olarak yapılmıştır.

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